

The Blessing Ritual of Assam

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Blessings or *asirbad diya* is an important event of any auspicious day observed in the Assamese community life. Blessings range from simple one-liners to lengthy speeches to songs. In all household and community events as well as in events of the community prayer-hall, elaborate blessing-seeking and blessing-giving rituals are performed by the performer(s) and the audience at the beginning and at the end. Although these orally preserved blessings are sought from all elderly persons, there are a few recognized blessing-givers in every village. Such persons render the blessing in community gatherings on behalf of everybody.

Blessing types:

In the Assamese society blessings are mainly of two types. They are, blessings sought and blessings given. However, in the placing of a blessing-speech, there is an additional part uttered by everyone present in the gathering in addition to the seeker and the giver. This is a chorus or a final request line. Blessings sought, blessings given and the final request line are discussed below.

1. Blessings sought:

Usually when a young person seeks blessings from an elderly person, he/she only bows down in front of the person and touches the person's feet. But in case of religious performances and community events, the performer seeks blessings of god or the forefathers. To seek the blessings of god, the performer usually makes a humbling speech through which he/she also seeks forgiveness for any mistakes unknowingly committed during the performance of the event. The following example is the blessing-seeking speech put forward by the eldest member

of the host family who organizes a religious ritual. He/she seeks the blessings of all the invitees and guests present at the end of the religious rituals. The speech goes as follows,

“Hei probhusokol, dase ki jonabo! Raij bulilei roja, gyati bulilei gonga, bhokot bulilei iswar. Apunasabar shri chaitanya murti ei obhagar ghorot pododhula diyehi. Apunasabak anibo lagisil kandhe kori, ahise pada choli. Apunasabe dasor dai-dos marisan kori ganthir guwapan khai santusta hoi dasok uddhar kori, ashirbad di jai jen”.

(O great ones, what is this servant of yours capable of! The public is as powerful as the king, the relatives are as holy as the Ganga, *bhakats* are as omniscient as the gods above. Your sacred being has today placed the dust under your feet in this fateful one’s house. I should have brought you carrying in my back, but you chose to come walking instead. I request you all to kindly forgive me for all my mistakes and to have the beetle-nut and bless this servant of yours.)

2. Blessings given:

These blessings are also of humbling nature. No blessings are given in a direct manner in which the blessing-giver puts him/ herself at the authoritative position. The giver only requests an unknown power or god or the forefathers to bless the seeker. The following is an example of the blessing-giving speech.

“Ghoror grihasthake mukhya kori, ista-mitra, gyati-kutumb, bondhubargake dhor grihaborti prani ji keiti ase, sobare proti Shrihari prasanna hoi, nilagar dhou nilagote mar niyai, mari-marak, byghradi, choradi bhoi durote nibortoman korai, grahadosh, kaladosh, daivadosh, rashidosh adi doshar pora mukta kori, bhogob-onto probhu suprasanna hoi monor sotbanchakhini siddhi kori dibo lage ae.”

(Shrihari should be pleased with the host, his family, relatives, friends and all the living beings present in the house; he should save them from all the near and distant threats, from epidemics, from tigers, from thieves etc.; he should make them free of all the malevolence of the stars, of fate, of the gods, of the zodiacs; he should bless them all and should fulfill the wishes of their pure hearts.)

3. The final request:

This is characteristic of all blessing-seeking and blessing-giving rituals except the one-to-one occasions. When, in a ritual or in a performance-event, a seeker seeks the blessings by putting

forward a speech, the people present utters the final request line in chorus at the end of the seeker's speech. This is done as an approval of the purpose for which the blessings are sought and also to further the request by placing it in front of god together with the seeker. The final request lines are usually short one-liners. As examples,

“*O' Hari, o' Ram*” (O Hari, O Ram) “*Jaya Hari bola, jaya Rama bola*” (Hail Hari, hail Ram) “*Guru Hari santoshar arthey, jaya Hari bola*” (To please Lord Hari, say hail Hari.)

Blessing occasions:

A few blessing occasions are discussed below.

- *One-to-one, in religious ceremonies and life-event ceremonies:* The one-to-one blessing occasions involve one person (usually a younger one) seeking the blessings of another person (usually an elder one in age and hierarchy). In such occasions, the prime performer seeks the blessings of the worshipped god before starting and after completing the rituals.
- *On a chance meeting:* On a chance meeting with an elderly person, or with an intellectually superior person, a younger person seeks blessings as a humbling gesture. The blessings are given according to the age and sex of the seeker.
- *As part of a ritual:* There are elaborate *sewa-kora* (to bow down) rituals associated with functions such as weddings, or with the *bihu*. .
- *In festive and other performance occasions:* The performers seek the blessings of god and the audience before a festival is formally started. In festivals such as community feasts during *bihu*, harvest-related events, the *bhaona* rehearsal etc. people seek blessings from the gods, the deities and the elders.

Performance:

Blessing rituals are performed with certain bodily postures and with a *shorai* as accompaniment.

Posture:

The posture of the seeker is of humbling nature. The seeker bows down in front of the giver, kneeling down on the floor with folded hands touching the feet of the giver. This posture is known as *sewa kora* which has an underlined connotation of ‘seeking something’ such as a blessing, a favor or forgiveness. If the seeker is a woman, she covers her head with her *sador* or a *gamocha* while bowing. The male seeker usually spreads both sides of the *gamocha*, which he wears in his neck, on the ground in front of him to receive the blessings.

The giver usually stands or sits on a *dhora* spread on the floor, or a *pira* or a chair. This is done in order to elevate the position of the blessing-giver, even by an inch, than the seeker. He touches the bowing head of the seeker with one or both of his hands, while uttering the blessing line or speech. After completing the blessing line or speech, the giver says, “*Hoise aru*” (It is done) and slightly lifts the head of the seeker with his hands to indicate the end to the ritual.

A *husori* troupe performs the blessing-giving ritual in various steps. The initial proverbial lines and the following blessing-speech are uttered by the expert blessing-giver of the troupe. After the speech, the next part which is lyrical is sung by one or more members of the troupe, while one other member stands up and dances along with it. The dancer sits down once the lyrical part is over and joins the rest of the group, including the blessing-giver, in uttering the final request line chorus.

Utterance:

The blessing-lines and blessing-speeches are uttered by a single person. Blessings in religious and community events are lengthy prose pieces uttered with a particular jargon. But the blessings sought and given lyrically are sung by everyone present along with the seeker and the giver, as the lyrical blessing-seeking is performed considering god as the supreme blessing-giver to whom everyone bows.

Accompaniments:

An elaborate blessing-seeking ritual, in all occasions, is accompanied by a *shorai* which is filled with a pair of beetle-nut and beetle-leaf properly cut and arranged with a certain amount of money while the seeker bows down kneeling in front of the giver with a *shorai* placed in front of an elder person in each other’s family. The *shorai* includes a beetle-nut and beetle-leaf pair arranged in a typical way known as *thuriuwa* and a gift for the person.

The existence of any folklore item for a long time in society is dependent on its usability or function that it serves in a society at a given point of time. The present study of Blessings

in Assam is an attempt not only to look at the functionality of the ritual, but also at the various important factors related to the performance of the same. A systematic study of oral blessings as 'oral texts' and also as 'texts in performance' will surely divulge a number of relevant and undiscovered facts about the ritual which contribute to the functionality of the ritual even at the present times, as a very important part of the Assamese community life.

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